

THE ROLE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN IMPROVING THE COUNTRY'S INVESTMENT CLIMATE

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The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with the State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in agreement with the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the authorized body for the development of the securities market in the part related to securities, has the right to provide explanations on the procedure for applying the provisions of this article, including clarifications on the detailed clarification of certain turnovers.

Also, according to Article 304 of this code, which is income not taken into account in taxation: the amount of the price of placement of shares (shares) in excess of their nominal value (initial amount) is not considered as income (until the end of 2023) [1].

Measure 1.6 of the "Roadmap" for the reform of the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025 is called "Gradual liberation of banks from assets and functions that are not specific to their activity", according to which, functions performed by banks that are not specific to their activity (tax agent, assistance to private housing owners associations, debt accounting, etc.) is tasked with detailed analysis and phased release [2].

In recent years, it has served to increase the quality of ratings given by rating agencies in determining the rating of banks. The change in this situation can be assessed by the rapid development of the world globalization process and the rapid adaptation of the process of "reaction" of the investors in the market to the results of the rating agencies. In some studies, it is stated that the bank rating is a quantity that indicates the ability to fulfill its obligations to a specific company in a certain period of time [3].

In the conditions of increasing healthy competition between banks, the system of evaluating the effectiveness of their activity becomes important in the sustainable development of commercial banks.

Commercial banks have a special place in the tax system of the state. Taxation of commercial banks, unlike other economic entities, has its own characteristics. The uniqueness of the tax system of commercial banks is

manifested in two incompatible situations. First, commercial banks are mediators between taxpayers and the state in terms of tax collection and control. Secondly, commercial banks are considered as payers of a number of taxes [4].

The table below shows the financial indicators of commercial banks, which shows that the financial condition of banks is reaching high levels today. This indicates that the country's economy is growing slowly (Table 1).

Table 1

Information on the main indicators of the banking system (billion soum) [5]

Indicator name	01.10.2021			01.10.2022			Nominal growth, in percent	"Real growth, (excluding devaluation) in percent"
	Total	therefore, in foreign currency	share, in percent	Total	therefore, in foreign currency	share, in percent		
Total assets	408 477	198 362	48,6 %	539 990	269 379	49,9 %	32,2%	30,3%
Total loan deposits	311 591	154 708	49,7 %	362 933	172 313	47,5 %	16,5%	14,9%
Total deposits involved	134 406	53 249	39,6 %	206 759	88 005	42,6 %	53,8%	51,9%
Total capital	65 608	342	0,5%	76 854	352	0,5%	17,1%	17,1%

According to the profit and loss report of commercial banks approved by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the income of commercial banks is divided into two large groups. In this report, the income of commercial banks is divided into interest income and non-interest income. If related legal entities in their commercial and financial relations use prices that differ from the prices

that can be used between independent legal entities, the profit of the taxpayer shall be equal to the difference in prices for the purpose of taxation, in accordance with the procedure established by law can be changed [6].

Table 2

Information on assets, loan capital and problem loans of banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan (trillion soums) [7]

Indicators	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	January 1, 2022
Assets	84,1	166,6	214,4	272,7	276,9	366,1	444,9
Risk assets	57,4	106,5	155,0	223,0	316,8	376,8	292,2
Loans issued	52,6	110,6	167,4	211,6	276,9	276,9	326,3
Capital	9,0	20,7	26,7	51,0	53,3	51,1	70,9
Problem loans	0,39	1,3	2,1	3,1	2,3	2,1	5,2

The assets of the banking system in 2021 will reach 383.2 trillion soums and increased compared to previous years, an increase of 335.3% compared to 2016. Risky assets also saw credit growth increase accordingly. Although the bank's capital has also increased, it can be seen that its adequacy ratio has decreased. The amount of both non-performing loans, which represent the quality of assets, has increased. Deterioration in asset quality indicates that it is moving into a problem asset [8].

A new approach to assessing the efficiency of commercial banks and researching issues of its improvement based on the new requirements of interbank competition allows:

➤ In the conditions of interbank competition, the theoretical views on the essence and importance of the efficiency of commercial banking activities are summarized, the efficiency of commercial banking activities is defined as “the competitive results of activities that represent the increase in the well-being of business owners, the creation and increase of bank value in the mode of compliance with banking legislation and prudential norms of regulation” and based on this, the scientific apparatus of this concept is filled and expanded [9];

➤ In the process of taking appropriate measures in time to prevent the bankruptcy of a commercial bank, a comprehensive classification of commercial banks is proposed, taking into account the identification of the author's parameter “efficiency of activity”, which is of practical importance in the regulatory activities of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan and from

the point of view of owners and investors [10];

➤ Based on the comprehensive analysis of the results of the commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the conditions of interbank competition, the trends of commercial banks activity efficiency are determined;

➤ as a result of the analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of the current methods of assessing the economic status of a commercial bank, the main indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of the commercial bank's activity are selected and scientific and methodological recommendations for their use are developed [11];

based on integrated indicators, a methodology for assessing the effectiveness of commercial banks will be developed, including the calculation of the efficiency of commercial banks [12].

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